

IMAGE OF WOMEN IN MODERN UZBEK STORIES

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Abstract: In this article, the characteristic aspect of the image of Uzbek women is analyzed based on the stories of Zulfia Kuroloy, a bright representative of modern Uzbek literature. By creating the characters of various characters such as Nazokat, Aunt Buvgul, and Tamara in the stories "Ayol", "Yozsiz Yil", "Victim of Loneliness", appropriate conclusions were drawn based on the analysis of the artist's skills.

Key words: image, character, prose, interpretation, analysis, word, artistry, realism, spirit, skill, creative skill.

Since the first years of independence, fundamental changes have taken place in the development of Uzbek literature, like all other fields. This was especially evident in prose. The originality of form and content, a new interpretation of the artist's style has appeared, which, of course, has the influence of advanced creative traditions characteristic of world literature. Most of these innovations in prose were reflected in the fast and concise narrative genre. In fact, regardless of the genre of prose, the main image in it is the image of a person.

"In order for a literary work to be a true example of a work, whether it belongs to realism, is written in the style of romanticism, or follows some other modernist style, it still needs a human being in its center, the reader receives certain information about the fate, nature, and life of a person, and also gets aesthetic pleasure from this work. Let him be able to take it too." Therefore, in modern literature, comprehensive study and discovery of man does not lose its constant relevance. Literature is rich and beautiful not only in terms of style, form and interpretation, but also in the variety of characters created in artistic works. Depicting characters who fight for life, strive for goodness, have patience and intelligence is the educational and aesthetic task of fiction. Today, Zulfia Kuroloy is one of the female writers who has created such diverse characters and has a place in the field of literature. In the stories created by him, the image of a woman has a special place. In particular, the author skillfully created various characters such as Nazokat, Aunt Buvgul, and Tamara in the stories "Ayol", "Yozsiz yil", "Victim of Loneliness" by his pen, which once again shows the reader that the writer has a high taste and talent. will confess. Through these images, their spiritual experiences, the sufferings and thoughts of the owners of different destinies are attractively and realistically artistically interpreted. In each of the women in her stories, in addition to the feelings of originality, love, loyalty and loyalty, characteristics such as determination and will are also developed.

The image of Nazokat in the story "Woman" is a clear example of this. In addition to the patience and feelings of love characteristic of Uzbek women, oriental elegance and strong will are more clearly expressed in determining the character of the character. While tenderness is fighting with severe pain, sira does not give up on femininity. He does not abandon his grace

and beauty, he knows that he will give up his life with this beauty, and no matter how much pain prevails, no matter how much he tries to pass his judgment on him, he will not be defeated by these difficulties, he prefers to fight valiantly, he will not despair even for a moment. After her death, a woman dreams of remaining in the memory of her family, children and husband as a kind mother, a beautiful wife. She is a tenacious woman who strives to live up to her name and is ready for anything. She feels that she has only a few days left in her life, she spends her few moments to find death while preserving her feminine femininity.

She does not want to be remembered by her husband and children as a woman whose face is pale, her eyes are sleepless and without light, and her body is overcome with swelling and pain. This can be observed in the following passage: "A nurse entered the ward. If my husband comes, please don't let him in - Nazokat told him. Why? "The doctor has appointed someone to be with you at night," said the nurse. Do not enter for a while, please. But he is worried... You will come up with an excuse! - said Nazokat and put money in the nurse's pocket. The nurse left hesitantly. Nazokat stared at the window. His sons appeared before his eyes. The woman bit her lip hard not to burst out. Through this dialogue, the writer convincingly wrote down the pain and suffering of the woman, which ensured the liveliness and aesthetic effect of the work. She does not want to show her husband her ugly and faded state after the swellings have taken over her whole body. She convinces the nurse not to let her husband in for money. She is depicted in a double struggle: pain occupying her body and efforts to preserve her beauty and femininity. Nazokat is ready to endure all the pains of the world in order to die a beautiful death and keep her femininity forever. He expects only one thing from the doctors: that he will not die ugly, that he will bear all the pain, and expects salvation from them. He sewed everything on this road, even a gold ring: "Nazokat put the gold ring in the doctor's pocket. Take the water, please. Only to the end! The doctor did not answer again. He didn't even look at it. Even after the woman's hand went into his pocket, he did not look at her face. However, "Nurse!" he called, looking at the corridor. Beauty smiles. Then he took the upa-elik from under his pillow...".

The most impressive part of the story, which moves the reader and immediately makes him cry, the highest point of pain and suffering, is that the ghost of death, despite the fact that he is walking in the fire, is next to the upa-elik pillow and takes it. He manifests his will like a moth. We are once again convinced that the author of the high and vivid image of reality is a real talent, the sharpness of his pen, and the possession of high taste and quality. Another such story of Zulfia Kuroilboy's daughter is "Yozsiz yil". Although the character of aunt Buvgul in the story is very different from Nazokat, they have some similarities. Aunt Buvgul is saddened to see the endless pain and suffering of her son, who lost his health and manhood due to a car accident, and despite being completely overwhelmed by grief, she is so patient that she forgets everything because of her son's one smile. - we can see the image of a real Uzbek woman who is patient, even forgets herself and gives everything for the happiness of her child.

The author tried to convey the images in the story to all the readers and he succeeded. A woman's mood, inner pain, is idealized in artistic colors to the extent that it shakes the heart. The writer expressed the picture of his whirlwind of thoughts in this way: "How much longer will this situation continue?" But from the moment he saw the happy face of his son, he forgot everything, what will happen tomorrow, now there is no one happy with my son, what more do I need." Yes, she is ready to do anything to get rid of her child's pain, and at the same time

she is a munificent and munificent mother. She hates everyone who looks down on her child. He even hates winter, which causes his child's health to deteriorate. She is the epitome of a real Uzbek mother whose only reason to live is for her child. His image is enriched with artistic tools and turned into a beautiful landscape. It is clear from every action and speech that the writer has accomplished the task assigned to him in the truest sense. She created the image of a true devoted mother.

In Adiba's story "Victim of Loneliness", a completely different world, a different life is written. The main character in it is a representative of another world. The story refers to the image of a lonely woman. It is clear from the title of the story that a woman trapped by loneliness is tragically described as passing through the world silently and without any sign. It is clearly explained that a woman is childless, unable to keep a child even though she is very old, and raising a child seems like an impossible task for her. It embodies the features of a woman who shied away from responsibility, lived only for herself, lived through youth and indolence without realizing the terrible and sad end of old age and loneliness. After losing her husband, she remains alone. In order to get rid of the loneliness and desolation that eats him, he goes to visit his loved ones, he cannot find satisfaction anywhere, he is not satisfied, and he returns to those useless things. Loneliness dries him up to such an extent that he even convinces himself that the rats have found him, he is happy, this situation seems very unusual when you think about it. He will die in loneliness from this useless and meaningless life. That night, a thief broke into his house and lost the things that he considered dear all his life, that he thought were more valuable than a child. At the end of the work, the woman becomes a victim of loneliness.

Summary

Generally speaking, three types of female characters are depicted in the above analyzed stories of Zulfiya Kuroloy's daughter. The writer has very clearly and convincingly expressed the human psyche, the fundamental twists and turns in his fate, and mental anguish. His sharp language and artistry combined to create beautiful works of art. In current literature, more attention is paid to the analysis of the human psyche than to the description of reality. It should be said that in the works of the writer, not social issues, but the image of a particular person, especially the image of a woman, and the description of his experiences and feelings are leading. In his works, the writer tries to satiate the artistic reality he created for the reader and make it understandable. For today's writers, realistic life is not the first priority. It is considered a means of ensuring artistic reality. The works of art are not about the details of interesting events, but about human experiences. In this regard, the image of a woman, the character of a woman requires constant study.

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